

INFORMATION SECURITY CLOUD INFRASTRUCTURE

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Thus, an effective solution to information security cloud infrastructure shall include:

- Indoor access to data

It is necessary to ensure reliable control of the encryption keys.

- Access policies

Only authorized users have access to confidential information.

- Intelligent

The system should collect information for the analysis of user behavior and alert if it detects suspicious activity. Information security in the cloud is not a trivial task, however, with an appropriate approach, you get a perfect balance of all the advantages of the cloud model and the high level of protection, security and availability of your data and information systems. The best option when customers use each individual virtual machine (VirtualMachine - VM) and virtual network. Separation between VM and consequently between the users, provides hypervisor. Virtual networks, in turn, deployed using standard technologies such as VLAN (VirtualLocalAreaNetwork), VPLS (VirtualPrivateLANService) and VPN (VirtualPrivateNetwork). Some providers put data of all clients in a single software environment, and due to changes in its code trying to isolate customer data from each other. This approach is reckless and unreliable. First, the attacker may be able to find a gap in the non-standard code that will allow him to gain access to data that he should not see. Secondly, the error code may cause one customer accidentally "see" other data. Recently, there were also

those other cases. Therefore, to distinguish between the use of user data of different virtual machines and virtual networks is a smart move.

Depending on the jurisdiction, laws and regulations and any special provisions may vary. For example, they may prohibit the export of data, require the use of well-defined measures of protection, the availability of compatibility with certain standards and availability of audit. Ultimately, they may require that, if necessary, access to the information could be government agencies and the courts. Neglect provider to these points may cause its customers to substantial costs due to legal implications.

The provider is obliged to follow strict rules and stick to a single strategy in the legal and regulatory spheres. This concerns the security of user data, their exports, compliance, audit, security and deleting data, as well as disclosure of information (the latter is especially true when a single physical server can store multiple clients). To find out, customers are urged to seek professional help, which will study the matter thoroughly. Therefore, service providers are required to adhere to certain rules of conduct in the event of unforeseen circumstances. These rules should be documented. Providers must focus on identifying incidents and minimize their effects, informing users about the current situation. Ideally, they should regularly provide customers with maximum detail information on the issue. In addition, customers themselves have to assess the likelihood of problems related to security, and to take the necessary measures. Despite the fact that today we have a much wider range of tools for security than ever before, the work is far from over. Intrinsically safe data (self-protected data) - is the encrypted data, which is integrated in the security mechanism. This mechanism includes a set of rules, which may or may not meet the environment in which the data are intrinsically safe. When you try to access the data, the mechanism of checks on the safety of the environment and open them only if the environment is safe.

Trusted Monitor (trustedmonitor) - this software is installed on the server cloud computing provider. It allows you to observe the actions of the provider and transmit

the results to the user, who can ensure that the company operates in accordance with the regulations.

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